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TRANSLATING THE UNTRANSLATABLE

The *Jalālayn* learning as a translation practice

Arif Maftuhin

ABSTRACT

Apart from the issue of the translatability of the Qur'an, the practice of translating the Qur'an into Indonesian has captured the attention of scholars. Some studies argue that there was a pause in activity after the composition of *Tarjumān al-Mustafīd*, a translation from Arabic to Malay in the 17th century. This viewpoint is primarily influenced by the expectation of finding a complete translation work similar to *Tarjumān*. However, this article contends that translating the Qur'an has always been an ongoing practice before and after *Tarjumān*. The aim of these translation practices, however, is not necessarily to create a work translated from one language to another, but rather to serve as a pedagogical activity that produces knowledge about the meaning of the Qur'an. This idea stems from the concept within translation studies that the term 'translation' encompasses not only the conventional act of translating between languages but can also involve intralingual translation and inter-semiotic translation. This proposition finds reinforcement in the presence of numerous *Jalālayn* manuscripts dating back to the late 19th century, which were employed within educational institutions known as *pesantren* and *surau* in East Java and West Sumatra.

KEYWORDS

interlinear translation; *Jalālayn*; *makna gandhul*; Qur'an translation; *tafsīr* manuscripts

ABSTRAK

Terlepas dari masalah dapat atau tidaknya Al-Qur'an diterjemahkan, praktik menerjemahkan Al-Qur'an ke dalam bahasa Indonesia telah menjadi perhatian para ilmuwan. Sebagian berpendapat bahwa ada jeda dalam aktivitas penerjemahan setelah penulisan *Tarjumān al-Mustafīd*, sebuah terjemahan dari bahasa Arab ke bahasa Melayu pada abad ke-17. Anggapan ini muncul karena harapan untuk menemukan sebuah terjemahan lengkap yang serupa dengan *Tarjumān*. Artikel ini berpendapat bahwa penerjemahan Al-Qur'an adalah praktik yang berkelanjutan sebelum dan setelah *Tarjumān*. Tujuan praktik penerjemahan tidak selalu untuk menciptakan sebuah karya terjemahan dari satu bahasa ke bahasa lain, tetapi lebih sebagai aktivitas pedagogis yang menghasilkan pengetahuan tentang makna Al-Qur'an. Argumen ini dibangun dari teori terjemahan yang menyatakan bahwa istilah 'terjemahan' dapat mencakup tindakan menerjemahkan antar-bahasa (*inter-language*), seperti yang selama ini banyak dipahami, maupun terjemahan intralingual dan terjemahan inter-semiotik. Dalam artikel ini, argumen tersebut didukung dengan melimpahnya manuskrip *Jalālayn* yang berasal dari akhir abad ke-19 dan digunakan dalam lembaga pendidikan di Jawa Timur dan Sumatera Barat yang dikenal sebagai *pesantren* dan *surau*.

KATA KUNCI

terjemahan antar-baris; *Jalālayn*; terjemahan gundul; penerjemahan Al-Qur'an; manuskrip tafsir

Introduction

Muslim scholars and jurists have long been concerned with the translatability of the Qur'an. In fact, inquiries regarding its translatability were already raised during the Prophet's time.¹ Modern scholars, particularly those who attempted to translate it into a Western language, such as Arberry (1996: 24) and M. Pickthall (1930), agree on its untranslatability (Rahman 1988: 26). The Muslim jurists, who deal with the need to read a translation of the Qur'an for non-Arabs in a prayer (*ṣalāh*), believe such practice is not permitted. While the issue originated from the validity of reading the Quranic translation within a prayer, the prominent jurist al-Nawawī (d.1277) expanded the illegality beyond the prayer. 'According to our school, it is not allowed to read the Qur'an in non-Arabic languages, whether he can speak Arabic or not, whether it is read within a prayer or not!' (Nawawī and Muṭīrī, n.d. III: 341). The idea that the Qur'an is the word of God in Arabic and a miracle (*i'jāz*) impossible to imitate (Wilson 2009: 420; Mustapha 2009: 226; Afsar and Azmat 2012: 193), supported the extension of illegality beyond the prayer.

If the translation of the Qur'an is illegitimate, how do we find so many 'translations' of the Qur'an? On a practical level, translations have been inevitable since Islam's earliest days. When the Arabic Qur'an reached a new audience, the non-Arab converts, there was a sudden need to read and recite the Qur'an. The first translation was done when Salmān al-Fārisī, the earliest Persian convert and of a Companion of the Prophet, was reported to have provided a translation to his fellow Persians (Nawawī and Muṭīrī, n.d. III: 341). While some questioned the report's validity (Tibawi 1962: 5), I prefer seeing it as a possible scenario that could happen in any case and at any time when the Qur'an meets non-Arabic speakers. The translation is a matter of necessity rather than translatability and legitimacy. Non-Arab Muslims must find a way to access the holiest text of their faith.

In 1936, a fatwa approved by the Council of Ministers in Egypt opened a possible way of translating the Qur'an. While confirming the majority opinion on the untranslatability of the Qur'an, the Egyptian fatwa provides one possible way to translate the Qur'an. The attachment stipulated that any translation must be called 'translation of an interpretation of the Qur'an'; or 'an interpretation of the Qur'an in language X'; and not 'a translation of the Qur'an' (Mustapha 2009: 227). In the fatwa, untranslatability is translated into very technical terms. We may have a translation, but never call it a translation. *Terjemah Al-Qur'an* is not legitimate, but *Terjemah Makna al-Qur'an* or *Tafsir al-Qur'an dalam Bahasa Indonesia* are.

Many of the modern translations of the Qur'an follow those 'subtle' ways of translating the Qur'an. For example, Pickthall's translation (1930) is *The meaning of the glorious Koran*. Saudi Arabia's official translation is *The noble Qur'an: the English translation of the meanings and commentary* (al-Hilali and Mohammad Khan 1977), not a translation of the Qur'an. The official Indonesian translation (1969) prefers to add *dan* (and) between the Qur'an and its translation, *Al-Quraan dan terjemahnja*. In addition to the title, the Indonesian translation, like many others, is

¹ For further discussion on this issue, see A.L. Tibawi (1962: 4–16).

printed *en face*. It emphasises its bitextuality,² where the Arabic text stands independently on the right column, and the translation is on the left.

The debate among Muslim scholars can theoretically be addressed from the translation studies perspective. Firstly, we need to consider ‘translation’ in three different aspects: definition, method, and presentation. In its most popular use, as we found in the previous debate among Muslim scholars, translation is the ‘process of substituting a text in one language for a text in another’ (Catford 1965: 1). Within this definition, translation can be done in metaphor, paraphrase, and/or imitation. Metaphrase is a word-by-word translation, line-by-line, from one language to another. In paraphrase, the translator keeps the author in view, but his words are not so strictly followed as his sense, being amplified but not altered. In imitation, the translator assumes the liberty not only to vary from the words and meaning but to forsake them both as he sees occasion, taking only some general hints from the original as he pleases (Dryden 2012: 38).

However, since language is no more than a sign, translation cannot be limited to relationships between two languages. That first definition is not enough to cover all the levels and complexities of translation as an activity to derive meaning from a sign system. Roman Jakobson (2012: 127) proposed three different types of translations:

1. *Intralingual translation* or rewording interprets verbal signs through other signs of the same language.
2. *Interlingual translation* or translation proper interprets verbal signs through another language.
3. *Inter-semiotic translation* or transmutation interprets verbal signs employing signs of non-verbal sign systems.

It could be argued that the definition of ‘interlingual’ translation is too narrow, and similarly, discussions about translation often assume only one way of presenting it: as a stand-alone work separate from the original text. However, there are at least three different ways of presenting translations:

1. The most common model is ‘independent translation’, where the translated work is published separately from the original.
2. ‘*En face* translations’ present both the source and translation side by side on a two-column page.
3. ‘Interlinear translation’ presents the source and translation one above the other, with each line corresponding to a line in the original text (Sturrock 1990: 993–1013).

To apply these theoretical points on the untranslatability of the Qur’an, we can say that a *tafsīr* (exegesis) could be considered a translation in all three types of translations, according to which language is used. An Arabic *tafsīr* is an intralingual and inter-semiotic translation. Most *tafsīr* provide a word-by-word translation (metaphrase) from Arabic to Arabic when faced with difficult words for average readers. It is what theoretically is called ‘intralingual translation’. Secondly, most of the *tafsīr* operate on the semiotic level. To identify the meaning of a Quranic verse, a *mufasssīr* (author of a *tafsīr*) uses various systems of knowledge beyond the Quranic texts, whether it is from previous authorities (*tafsīr bi al-ma’ūtur*) or reasoning (*tafsīr bi al-ra’y*). The non-Arabic *tafsīr* operate

² Bitextuality can be defined as ‘... as texts that are presented bilingually, with portions in one language mixed together with portions in another ...’ (see Walker 2020: 675–700).

similarly. Firstly, they provide interlingual translation and the foreign meaning of a verse. Secondly, the *mufassir* works on an inter-semiotic 'translation' or *tafsir*.

Based on these theoretical considerations, this article will explore an alternative method of translating the Qur'an through the practice of reading and learning *Tafsir al-Jalalayn* (henceforth *Jalalayn*) in Indonesian *pesantren* (Islamic boarding schools) and *surau* (prayer houses). These are institutions where Muslims learn about Islamic subjects, including the Qur'an, Arabic language, theology, and Islamic history (see below). Based on manuscripts utilised in *pesantren* and *surau* during the 19th century, this article will argue that the pedagogical practice of employing *Jalalayn* can elucidate two theoretical points. Firstly, the *Jalalayn* manuscripts are a medium for translating the Qur'an without committing 'the offence' of translating the Qur'an. Teachers and students in *pesantren* or *surau* can avoid translating the 'untranslatable' Quranic text by translating the *Jalalayn* instead.

Secondly, using *Jalalayn* in pedagogical settings fulfils the need for a Quranic translation for Indonesians who do not speak Arabic. Previous studies argued for a relative absence of a significant translation activity after the first and famous *Tarjumān al-Mustafid* (henceforth, *Tarjumān*) in the 17th century. Peter Riddell (1989: 119), on *Tarjumān*, said,

... for almost 300 years, it was the only commentary on the Qur'an available in Malay, and as such came to represent something of a standard against which other exegetical works in Malay have been compared.

More recent studies have tried to challenge this claim. Ervan Nurtawab (2020: 169–189), for example, discussed some manuscripts of Quranic translation from 18th-century Banten to show some translation activities. Another translation manuscript from the 18th century was found in Central Java. It is a translation of *al-Fātiḥah*, bundled with other various topics, and is thought to have been written by Kiai Ahmad Mutamakkin (Sa'adah and Asif 2020: 1–32), a famous Sufi who lived between the 17th and 18th centuries. These manuscripts prove the continuous activities of translation. In addition to such manuscripts, I will argue that the '*Jalalayn* learning' as a translation practice fulfilled the need for a dedicated local language translation.

In line with these recent studies, I would argue that translation might have been practised before *Tarjumān* and continues afterwards in the educational setting through *Jalalayn* learning.³ Unlike those studies, however, I do not rely on a 'dedicated' translation work (such as *Tarjumān*), but on a translation practice of *Jalalayn* learning. What I mean by '*Jalalayn* learning' is the practice of teaching, reading, translating, and studying the *Jalalayn* in an Islamic educational setting. The apparent absence of a translation work before and after *Tarjumān* is because the long tradition of *Jalalayn*-learning needs no such translation. A previous study on a pre-Islamic religious practice showed a similar situation where:

... the apparent lack in the archipelago of commentarial tradition parallel to that of South Asia reveals to us not the absence of a tradition of commentary but exactly the opposite: the norms of the South Asian commentary were so deeply embedded in the pedagogy of religious institutions that they left indelible traces on all that was to follow (Aciri and Hunter 2020: 236)

³ The very probability that a large part of *Tarjumān* is a translation of *Jalalayn* supports my assumption that the practice of learning *Jalalayn* heavily influenced 'Abd al-Rauf in writing his *Tarjumān*. On the sources of *Tarjumān* see Riddell (1984: 113–118).

This discovery from the pre-Islamic era appears to align perfectly with the *Jalālayn* method of learning in the *pesantren* and *surau*. Through the *Jalālayn* learning, students in these institutions acquire a translation of the Qur'an and comprehensive insight into its meaning. Consequently, they do not require additional commentary or localised Indonesian translations, as their didactic approach provides them with the translation of the Qur'an and adequate access to its meaning.

The manuscripts and their contexts

Tafsīr al-Jalālayn is a Quranic exegesis written by two Egyptian authors, a teacher and his pupil, who happened to have the same name Jalāl. The teacher, Jalāl al-Dīn al-Maḥallī (d.864/1459), wrote the second half of the *tafsīr* (starting from al-Kahfi). He died when he began work on the first half of the Qur'an. Based on his work, his pupil, Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūṭī (d.911/1505), continued and finished the *tafsīr*. The title of their commentary, *Tafsīr al-Jalālayn*, is named after them: a *tafsīr* by two *Jalāl*-s. *Jalālayn* is a simple but 'efficient' commentary of the Qur'an. It is suitable for students of Islamic learning and has a broader audience than other Quranic exegeses. Al-Suyūṭī's comments on his teacher's *tafsīr* explains why it is so popular. In his introduction, al-Suyūṭī said that he completed his teacher's work and followed his model (*namt*), which includes:

... commentaries to understand the Divine words; taking the most valid opinions; explaining the grammatical aspects when needed; giving notes on various famous readings, in a simple way, an effective sentence; and avoiding long explanations on grammatical elements that should be discussed in Arabic grammar books. (Jalāl al-Dīn al-Maḥallī and Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūṭī 2003: 2)

The *tafsīr* is widely read, taught, and learned worldwide. In South Africa, the *tafsīr* is still taught in Islamic educational institutions (Ahmed and Sukdaven 2021). The *tafsīr* left its mark on the local Swahili exegesis in East Africa (Chande 2021: 111–132). Its influence can also be found in Champa, Cambodia (Okawa 2014: 1–20). At the end of the 19th century, the Dutch scholar L.W.C. van den Berg listed books on Islamic education in Indonesia. He recorded only one *tafsīr*, *Jalālayn*, as part of the regular curriculum in Islamic educational institutions (van Bruinessen 1990: 226–269). The abundance of *Jalālayn* manuscripts collected from different parts of Indonesia in the Endangered Archive Project (EAP) confirms van den Berg's finding that *Jalālayn* has been Indonesia's most popular and studied *tafsīr*.

In this study, I selected manuscripts from two EAP projects, coded as EAP061 and EAP144. My choice is based on a consideration that the two collections will represent two different regions of Indonesia (Java and Sumatra) and two major languages (Javanese and Malay) in the archipelago. We do not have exact information about the age of each manuscript. The details provided in the project suggest that they were written between the 18th and 20th centuries. It is a broad time range, so it is hard to estimate their age accurately. The estimated timeframe may be based on the data that one of the *pesantren*, Pesantren Tegalsari, was founded in 1742 (Guillot 1985: 139), and one of the *surau*, Surau Bintungan Tinggi, was established in 1864 (Yulfira 2012).

Most of the manuscripts are pedagogical. EAP144-3, for example, digitalised 82 manuscripts, including 32 non-pedagogical manuscripts comprising contractual documents, debts, or business notes. It is also worth noting that many of them are incomplete or bundled in two different files. Two manuscripts in the tables (see Tables 1 and 2) can be one single manuscript in two volumes. I do not track all files for these possibilities because of their incompleteness, but I did find one example for this case. Manuscripts coded as EAP061-1-105 and EAP061-1-106 are one manuscript of *Jalālayn* in two complete volumes, digitalised as two manuscripts. Considering the details, the readers should wisely read the tables as a general picture of the collection rather than an exact number as I will focus on

the didactical notes rather than the precise number of manuscripts. The tables, however, show that the 27 samples of *Jalālayn* manuscripts were sampled from a large population of 565 manuscripts of various subjects in Islamic studies. Out of 27 manuscripts, I will focus on 21 manuscripts with pedagogical notes. These pedagogical notes include marginal and interlinear notes. I will discuss the manuscripts to find out how this practice of pedagogical notes is relevant to our quest to understand how it helps non-Arab Muslims understand the Qur'an without needing a specific Indo-Malay translation.

The East Javanese manuscripts

The EAP061 is a collection of 312 manuscripts digitalised from three *pesantren* at three locations in East Java:

1. EAP061-1 from Pesantren Langitan, Tuban
2. EAP061-2 from Pesantren Kranji, Lamongan
3. EAP061-3 from Pesantren Tegalsari, Ponorogo

A *pesantren* is an old Islamic educational institution known by different names across Southeast Asia, such as *pondok*, *surau*, or *dayah* (Hidayatulla Azra 2018: 763–780). It was and is a private Islamic education institution belonging to a religious scholar called *kiai* or their family. Its students, called *santri*, study branches of knowledge considered necessary in Islam, such as *ʿaqidah* (theology), *fiqh* and *uṣūl al-fiqh* (Islamic law), *al-naḥw*, *al-ṣarf*, *al-bayān* (Arabic language and literature), *al-mantiq* (logic), *al-taṣawwuf* (Sufism) and *al-akhlāq* (morality), *tārikh* and *sīrah* (history), *al-Ḥadīth* (prophetic tradition) and *al-Tafsīr* (Quranic exegesis).

Table 1. *Jalālayn* manuscripts of EAP61.

Project code	Total number of manuscripts	Number of <i>Jalālayn</i> manuscripts	<i>Jalālayn</i> Manuscripts with pedagogical notes
EAP061-1	133	6	6
EAP061-2	72	1	1
EAP061-3	107	7	6
Total number of manuscripts in the collections	312	14	13

Table 1 shows that in terms of quantity, the number of *Jalālayn* manuscripts from these three collections is not substantial, with only 14 out of 312 (0.04%). However, of these 14 manuscripts, nearly all (13) contain what we refer to in this article as 'pedagogical notes'. These were notes made by students or teachers during their study in a *bandongan* class. The EAP projects and collections do not describe how the manuscripts were used in their respective locations during those centuries. According to Zamakhsyari Dhofier (2011: 53–59.), there are three learning models in a *pesantren*: *sorogan* (face-to-face learning), *bandongan* (learning in groups), and *musyawarah* (discussion).⁴ Although his research was carried out in the 1970s, it is reasonable to suggest that there are few

⁴ Linguistically speaking, the term *sorogan* comes from the Javanese word *sorog*, which conveys the idea of presenting something, face to face. The term *bandongan* derives from the word *bandong*, which means 'group'; thus, *bandongan* signifies 'learning in a group'. Unlike the two previous terms, *musyawarah* originates from Arabic, which means 'discussion'.

differences between the methods of that era and those of the 19th century. It is supported by the fact that we can observe no divergence between the current practices in *pesantren* (21st century) and those he described from the 1970s. The traditional and conservative nature of *pesantren* supports the notion of its continuity and stability over time.

Dhofier explains that a *sorogan* class constitutes a *pesantren*'s initial level of education, yet it is the most challenging. *Sorogan* is a small class of 5 to 10 students who have completed the Quranic reading class. For Muslims in Indonesia, reading the Qur'an, instead of Arabic grammar or its linguistic forms, is the first essential skill every child must learn. They start learning Arabic as a language system when they are good and familiar enough to read the Qur'an. In a *sorogan* class, they are taught to read introductory Arabic books. They learn to read, translate into local languages, and know the grammatical aspects of an Arabic sentence in the book. In an established *pesantren*, a teacher is assigned to ensure that all students in that small class succeed in this preparatory course.

In a *bandongan* class, a *kiai* would sit before a larger group of *santri*, from dozens to hundreds. Listening to what the *kiai* or teacher said, the students write the meaning of a word and its grammatical status. If the word is novel, he may add *ḥarakāt* according to the *kiai*'s reading. *Ḥarakāt* is a system to mark a vowel sound in the Arabic text because written Arabic does not indicate vowels. We can only pronounce a word by memorising the sound and knowing its grammatical position in a sentence. Unlike a *sorogan* class, there is no supervision of what the students write and learn in a *bandongan* class. It may be the class where our *Jalālayn* manuscripts might have come from.

The *musyawarah* (seminar class) is a learning method in which many *santri* are not qualified to participate. The *kiai* would see who among his *santri* can read Arabic texts, possess knowledge of various Islamic studies, or have independent learning capacity. Unlike in the *bandongan* class, the *kiai* would no longer read a book for the *santri*. Instead, he would give a problematic case to be solved by the *santri*. The *santri* must work on the case before the class. They should find a solution to offer in the *musyawarah* session. If the course uses a certain *kitab*⁵, the *santri* will take notes on the margin of the main referred *kitab*.

Based on such a didactical context, it can be assumed how the manuscripts from East Java were once utilised. We can observe that the *Jalālayn* manuscripts from East Java mostly contain two notable different texts:

1. The main text, the *Jalālayn* text, consisted of two texts: the Qur'an and the commentary by *Jalālayn*.
2. The pedagogical text consisted of marginal and interlinear notes by students or teachers of *pesantren*.

⁵ Any book on Islamic teaching typically written in Arabic.

Figure 1. EAP 061-1-105 manuscript of from Tuban, East Java, 19th century. Source: Endangered Archives Programme (EAP) of the British Library and its archival partners, <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP061-1-105>> Folio 7.

In the main text, the Qur'anic text is written in red ink, while the *Jalālayn* commentary is in black ink. In addition to this main text, we find pedagogical or *bandongan* notes (see Figure 1). We do not know whether a teacher wrote these notes to prepare his class or students wrote them while learning in the *pesantren*. In most cases, we can assume that students made the notes. The pedagogical notes are always in black. The main script and the didactical notes differ in style and size. While the primary *Jalālayn* scripts are written in Naskhī style, the didactical notes are written in Riq'ī. There is also a difference in the size; the *Jalālayn* script is always larger than the didactical notes.

As Figure 1 shows, it is apparent that while the script employed is exclusively Arabic, the languages conveyed are not. While the primary texts, the Qur'an and the *Jalālayn*, are rendered in Arabic, the accompanying pedagogical annotations manifest in dual languages, predominantly Javanese, with a minor subset in Arabic. The Arabic script utilised for transcribing Javanese is termed *pegon*. Due to Islam's gradual assimilation, early Javanese Muslims initially employed Javanese scripts to document their religious literature. *Pegon* came into usage during later periods (Pigeaud 1967: 26), particularly for religious literature, as underscored by its prevalence in these *Jalālayn* manuscripts.

Figure 2. EAP061-3-72 manuscript of from Pondok Pesantren Tegalsari. Source: Endangered Archives Programme of the British Library and its archival partners, <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP061-3-72>> Folio 4.

Most of these manuscripts from Java have less than 20 lines per page, with ample space between the lines. For example, manuscript EAP061-1-105 (Figure 1) only has 10 to 11 lines per page. Only two of the Javanese manuscripts have more than 20 lines, EAP061-2-17 (24 lines) and EAP061-3-33 (21 lines). Based on these samples, the Javanese manuscripts seem to be intentionally designed to provide a spacious room for interlinear notes. The interlinear translation system practised in a *pesantren* is a translation system that combines oral and written aspects. This translation follows a unique approach that, according to Aly Abubakar Basalamah (1994: 62), pays attention to linguistic and extra-linguistic elements in the source language. These linguistic elements include vocabulary, syntax, and morphology, among others. The extra-linguistic elements are derived from the broader Islamic scientific tradition, such as *fiqh* and theology. These two elements are combined to produce meaning in the target language.

In Java, there are various terms to refer to this interlinear translation, such as *terjemah gandul* (hanging translation; Burdah 2011: 353–377), *terjemah jenggotan* (beard-like translation;

Irhamni 2011: 95–118), *terjemah gantung* (hanging translation), or *terjemah tradisional* (Basalamah 1994). Instead of hiding the source text, this translation system retains the original as a primary text and displays the translation as secondary. According to Basalamah (1994: 65), the existence of the source text is to anticipate any mistake in translation since however good a translation, it can never fully represent the source language. By presenting the source text, readers can correct if there is an error. Due to the personal use of *Jalālayn* manuscripts, the scribes/students do not write an entire translation of the words. The translations are only added when students need them. Some write them comprehensively, while others write only essential words. There are no technical differences between translating Arabic words from the Quranic verses or *Jalālayn* commentaries.

The West Sumatran manuscripts

The EAP₁₄₄ comes from similar Islamic educational institutions called *surau* in West Sumatra. The project digitalised 258 manuscripts from five *surau* in West Sumatra:

1. EAP₁₄₄-1 from Surau Baru Bintungan Tinggi collection
2. EAP₁₄₄-2 from Surau Batang Kapeh collection
3. EAP₁₄₄-3 from Surau Lubuk Ipuh collection
4. EAP₁₄₄-4 from Surau Parak Laweh Pariangan collection
5. EAP₁₄₄-5 from Surau-surau Malalo collection

According to Gazalba (1963: 293), the *surau* grew from a pre-Islamic community centre belong to a clan (*indu*), where male youth gathered, hung out, and slept (Azyumardi Azra 2017: 8). This traditional function continued and was 'Islamised' as it became a place where the youth learned basic skills and knowledge of how to be a good Muslim, mainly learning to read the Qur'an. It has also become the centre of *tarekat* (Sufi orders) that developed well in Minangkabau (ibid.: 9). Some *surau* of the past have now been transformed into *pesantren* like those in Java. The *Jalālayn* manuscripts from EAP₁₄₄ projects were used in such institutions.

Like students in Java, after finishing the essential learning of reading the Qur'an, Minangkabau students would take an advanced study on various Islamic subjects, including *tafsīr* (Yunus 1996: 34–45). Before learning Arabic books on *fiqh* and *tafsīr*, students would learn Arabic by learning *al-ṣarf* (morphology) and *al-naḥw* (grammar). In learning *al-ṣarf*, the students have to actively memorise word patterns (*al-wazn*). It does not matter whether they understand what they memorise or not. In teaching *al-naḥw*, the teacher is active. Firstly, he would read the Arabic text (*al-matn*). Then, he translates the Arabic text into Malay, word by word. And finally, he would explain the content. It is also the case with learning other subjects like *tafsīr* and *fiqh* (ibid.: 48). Yunus does not mention any term related to this system of learning. Azyumardi Azra (2017: 9), who conducted thoughtful research on *surau*, found that their learning method is called *halaqah* (Arabic: group), which resembles *bandongan* in Javanese *pesantren*.

In addition, Azyumardi Azra (2017) argued that most *surau* have not developed to be like the *pesantren* in Java. He found one *surau*, Surau Syaikh Abdurrahman in Batuhampar, that may be comparable to a Javanese *pesantren*. According to him, this *surau* is an exception (Azyumardi Azra 2017: 15). While the Javanese *pesantren* have survived till today, the *surau* were quickly challenged by colonial political pressure and the internal reform movement in education. After the Padri War (1821–37),⁶ many *surau* were abandoned as the war cost the lives of many *syaikh* (teachers). To study religion, many turned to sending their children to Mecca (Azyumardi Azra 2017: 16). Towards the

⁶ This was armed conflict in Minangkabau (Sumatra) between reformist Muslims, known as *Padri*, and local chieftains who had help from the Dutch (see Encyclopedia Britannica on Padri War <<https://www.britannica.com/event/Padri-War>>

beginning of the 20th century, a new educational model of religious schools started to replace the *surau*. While the Javanese *pesantren* survived the 19th and 20th century challenges, the *surau* failed to grow.

In the historical context of *surau*, which experienced limited development in contrast to the more extensive *pesantren* system, the EAP project achieved the compilation of 253 manuscripts from five distinct locations. It is imperative to underscore that, in contrast to EAP 061 in Java, a substantial number of non-pedagogical manuscripts were encountered within EAP 144. Out of the comprehensive pool of 253 manuscripts originating from Sumatra, only 13 *Jalālayn* manuscripts were ascertainable, representing a mere 0.05% of the total. Furthermore, in this subset of 13 *Jalālayn* manuscripts, pedagogical notes were discernible in only eight instances (0.61%).

Table 2. *Jalālayn* manuscripts of EAP144.

Projects code	Number of manuscripts in each project	Number of <i>Jalālayn</i> manuscripts	<i>Jalālayn</i> manuscripts with pedagogical notes
EAP144-1	36	6	3
EAP144-2	23	0	0
EAP144-3	82	4	4
EAP144-4	33	0	0
EAP144-5	79	3	1
Total number of manuscripts in the Project	253	13	8

Figure 3. EAP 144-3-23 manuscript from Surau Lubuk Ipuh, Kuraitaji, Padang Pariaman. Source: Endangered Archives Programme of the British Library and its archival partners, <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP144-3-23>> Folio 2.

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The *Jalālayn* manuscripts from West Sumatra used two distinct ink colours: red ink was for inscribing Quranic text, and black ink was utilised for transcribing the *Jalālayn* text. Notably, most Sumatran manuscripts displayed a denser textual arrangement than their Javanese counterparts, accommodating more than 20 lines per page (Figure 3). Even in instances where fewer than 20 lines were present on a page, Sumatran manuscripts failed to provide adequate interlinear space for translation. They left the marginal areas more spacious than the interlinear (see Figure 4). This way, the Sumatran manuscripts facilitate the prevalence of marginal annotations (Figure 5).

Figure 4. EAP 144-3-39 manuscript of from Surau Lubuk Ipuh, Kuraitaji, Padang Pariaman. Source: Endangered Archives Programme of the British Library and its archival partners, <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP144-3-39>> Folio 2.

As evident in the three manuscript examples (Figures 3, 4, and 5), West Sumatran manuscripts are primarily written in Arabic scripts, representing two languages: Arabic and the Minangkabau dialect of Malay. The Arabic script used for writing Malay is known as Jawi (Gallop 2015: 13–171). However, the amount of Jawi notes in a Sumatran manuscript is typically limited. Often, in addition to the Quranic and *Jalālayn* texts, pedagogical notes in Sumatran manuscripts tend to include interpretations, grammatical references, and interlingual translations (Arabic to Arabic) for complex words, all in Arabic rather than a translation. For instance, in Figure 3, the only Malay-Jawi translation note appears on the last line, translating the word *aršadanā* with *petunjuk* (guidance).

Figure 5. Sumatran manuscript with full notes on the margin and no Jawi notes. Source: Endangered Archives Programme of the British Library and its archival partners, <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP144-3-33>> Folio 25.

What, then, can be inferred concerning the marginal parts of Sumatran manuscripts, which typically exhibit wider space than their Javanese counterparts? As we can see from the examples, these marginal annotations primarily comprise supplementary explanations that the writer has culled from various other *tafsīr*. As exemplified in Figure 3, the upper right corner features an Arabic annotation expounding how al-Maḥallī initiated his *tafsīr* from Chapter al-Kahfī (*Kāna al-Ṣayḥ Jalāl al-Dīn al-Maḥallī qad bada'a bihi min sūrah al-kahfi*...). There are also marginal notes written in an orientation to the main text, explaining the merits of *ḥamdallāh*. On the right-hand margin, also in a reverse orientation, three explanations are sourced from other commentaries; noted in that section are Bayḍāwī, Ibn 'Abbās, and *Anwār* (Bayḍāwī's *tafsīr*). Therefore, while Malay translations are

seldom encountered in the interlinear notes, Malay translations are absent in the marginal notes. Of particular interest is the discovery of a manuscript that exclusively comprises annotations rendered in Arabic. Manuscript EAP 144-3-33 (Figure 5) is the sole Sumatran manuscript encompassing comprehensive marginal annotations extending from the initial to the final page. Infrequently, interlinear annotations also surface within this manuscript. However, unlike other manuscripts, Malay translations are absent in the interlinear notes. Both marginal and interlinear annotations employ Arabic as a medium for furnishing additional insights or commentary about the main *Jalālayn* text, whether this involves direct citations from other *tafsīr* with proper attribution or providing standalone explanations without references.

Commonalities and differences

The historical contexts, as described by Dhofier (2011), Yunus, (1996) and Azyumardi Azra (2017), give us a glimpse of how the development of *pesantren* and *surau* in the late 19th century can help us assume the factors contributing to the different practices of learning the *Jalālayn* and their marks on the manuscripts. Tables 1 and 2 show a significant difference in how these two groups of manuscripts were used. Thirteen out of 14 manuscripts from the *pesantren* have pedagogical notes. However, only eight of 13 manuscripts from the *surau* have pedagogical notes. This fact may correlate with Azyumardi Azra's explanation that the *pesantren* is a more established educational institution than the *surau*.

Because of their didactic nature, most of the manuscripts in the projects contain well known *kitab*s (books) that originated from the Middle East. Besides *Jalālayn*, we can find other popular *kitab* on Arabic grammar, theology, and Sufism. These manuscripts are not 'endangered' in terms of philological content, because today, one can easily find well edited and printed versions of the texts. What makes them unique are the various handwritten notes in the manuscripts. They were supposedly written in a didactical process in the various *pesantren* and *surau*. These vast pedagogical notes show how Arabic Islam has been transmitted to Indonesian Muslims and how, mainly, the Qur'an was learned, understood, or translated. The following section compares and contrasts these two groups pertaining to the collections, manuscript styles, pedagogical notes, and manuscript evolution.

Manuscript collections

The manuscript collections from Java (EAP061) originate in the *pesantren*, which hold a significant historical legacy in Java. These Islamic educational institutions have played a vital role in shaping religious education and scholarship within the region and have endured while maintaining their traditional characteristics. Although, Sumatra's manuscripts (EAP144) are sourced from various *surau*, which have a distinct historical path – initially established as pre-Islamic community centres, these *surau* transformed into places where young individuals learned the fundamentals of being devout Muslims, particularly Quranic recitation. Unlike the *pesantren*, *surau* encountered challenges and experienced limited growth, with only a few exceptions that can be comparable to the well established Javanese *pesantren*.

Manuscript styles

Both EAP061 and EAP144 collections adhere to more general Islamic manuscript traditions regarding ink usage. Red ink is consistently employed in Javanese manuscripts for the Quranic text, while black ink is reserved for the *Jalālayn* commentary. Similarly, Sumatran manuscripts adhere to this pattern, using red ink for the Quranic text and black ink for the *Jalālayn* commentary.

Furthermore, in both regions, pedagogical notes, when present, predominantly employ black ink, underscoring the shared adherence to these manuscript conventions and practices in both Java and Sumatra. Both collections show the similar use of two colours in a *Jalālayn* manuscript that seems familiar worldwide. A manuscript of *Jalālayn*, possibly originating from the Ottoman Empire (dated 1146 H or 1733/1734 CE), not intended to be translated into another language, also features this model of two colours (see Figure 6).

The Javanese manuscript collection (EAP061) stands out for its deliberate design, characterised by a deliberate choice of fewer lines per page and ample interlinear spaces. This design strongly hints at a pedagogical purpose, underlining the significance of annotations and translations while seamlessly merging linguistic and extra-linguistic elements within the manuscripts. In contrast, the Sumatran manuscripts (EAP144) typically adopt denser textual arrangements, often exceeding 20 lines per page. While interlinear notes are still a feature, the limited space suggests a distinct annotation and translation approach. This disparity in design and layout hints at potential differences in the learning methodologies employed in these two regions.

Figure 6. A *Jalālayn* manuscript, probably from the Ottoman Empire.⁷ Source: Thomas Fisher Rare Book Library, University of Toronto.

⁷ MSS 01055, <<https://archive.org/details/tafsiraljilalink00unse/page/2/mode/2up>>

Pedagogical notes

The Javanese *Jalālayn* manuscripts distinguish themselves through the prevalence of pedagogical notes, with 13 out of 14 manuscripts containing such annotations. These notes, believed to be the work of students or instructors during *bandongan* classes, highlight a robust tradition of annotating and annotative learning within this context. Conversely, the Sumatran collection of *Jalālayn* manuscripts displays a contrasting pattern, with pedagogical notes found in eight of 13 manuscripts. This disparity suggests that while pedagogical notes do exist in Sumatran manuscripts, they are not as widespread as in their Javanese counterparts. Additionally, it appears that the Sumatran *halaqah* learning method resembles the Javanese *bandongan* system. However, differences in the prevalence of pedagogical notes signify regional distinctions in the learning tradition.

Manuscript evolution

The Java collection (EAP061) highlights the enduring and unwavering nature of the *pesantren* in Java, as they have managed to preserve their educational methods and traditions, remaining remarkably similar to what was observed in the 1970s. This endurance suggests a notable degree of continuity in Islamic education across time in Java. However, Sumatra's *surau* did not undergo a similar level of evolution and stability. These institutions encountered formidable challenges, including colonial pressures and internal reform movements, which hindered their development and growth. Only a select few exceptions among the *surau* in Sumatra exhibit educational robustness comparable to that found in the Javanese *pesantren*, underscoring the regional disparities in the evolution of Islamic educational institutions.

In conclusion, comparing Javanese and Sumatran manuscripts highlights both commonalities and differences in their manuscript traditions. While both regions share certain practices, such as ink usage and the presence of pedagogical notes, they also exhibit distinct features related to manuscript style, educational evolution, and the prevalence of annotations. These differences can be attributed to the unique historical development of the *pesantren* in Java and *surau* in Sumatra, as well as their respective approaches to Islamic education and manuscript culture.

Translating the untranslatable

Jalālayn as a translation

Typically considered as a *tafsīr*, *Jalālayn* is a 'double translation'. Based on Jacobson's theory (2012), *Jalālayn* is both an intralingual and an inter-semiotic translation. The interpretation method used in *Jalālayn* is a mix of linguistic and non-linguistic explanations. The linguistic descriptions include (1) providing Arabic synonyms for difficult Qur'anic words; (2) the grammatical aspects of the Qur'an; (3) clarifying many Arabic and Qur'anic linguistic tropes by filling in omissions and ellipses employed in the Qur'an; and (4) suggesting meanings for synecdoche, metonymy, metaphor, and allusion used in Arabic (Ġāzī bin Muḥammad bin Ṭalāl 2008: ix-x). In other words, *Jalālayn* uses linguistic elements to translate the meaning of the Divine Arabic Qur'an into more 'human' Arabic. It is a translation from Arabic to another Arabic, an intralingual translation of the Qur'an.

Like many other *tafsīrs*, the *Jalālayn* also provides non-linguistic explanations. These include (1) legal explanations of verses according to the Shāfi'ī school of jurisprudence; (2) putting the verses into context; (3) perspective and mutual definitions from other verses of the Qur'an (practising *tafsīr bil-tafsīr* method); (4) providing the revelation context (*asbāb al-nuzūl*); (5) indicating which verses are abrogated (*mansūḥ*) and which verses abrogate (*nāsikh*); (6) explanation of different 'readings' (*qirā'āt*) of a word; (7) and filling in some stories or explanation based on the Christian and Jewish traditions (*Isrā'īliyyāt*) (ibid.). These non-linguistic resources lie in the broader system of the Islamic

faith, a system of knowledge that we can consider semiotic. Here *Jalālayn* is an inter-semiotic translation of the Qur'an.

Figure 2 is an example of how those methods are used in *Jalālayn*. Al-Baqarah starts with a particular case where the Qur'an opened its chapter with a series of letters: *alif-lām-mīm*. These are non-word letters with no definitive meaning. They are known as *hurūf al-mutahajji* or *al-hurūf al-muqatta'ah* in Quranic studies (*'ulūm al-Qur'ān*). Scholars of Quranic studies are divided into two camps: one group believes these letters have secret meanings (*sir mahjūb*), and only God knows what they are. The second group argues that the Qur'an should not contain things humans cannot understand. Therefore, they prefer to explain or translate these letters. According to the second group, for example, *alif-lām-mīm* are three letters God chose to swear by, like the cases where God swears by a city, the sun, time, and others. God uses them to swear (*qasam*) (al-Zarkasyī 2006: 123–126). In this matter, the authors of the *Jalālayn* follow the first group. They 'translated' *alif-lām-mīm* as 'God knows the meaning.'

In terms of understanding the meaning of the Qur'an, this intralingual translation is necessary to find the authoritative meanings of the divine words. Islamic scholarship has developed an extensive body of literature on this issue, which grew into a branch of knowledge called *Ulūm al-Qur'ān*. It is one of the most important subjects in any Islamic educational institution. It provides histories, genealogies, and theories of interpreting the Qur'an. *Tafsīr*, such as *Jalālayn*, is the product of this field of knowledge. The explanation by *Jalālayn* – that 'God knows the meaning' – provides an authoritative reference for anyone who translates the letters (*alif-lām-mīm*) into other languages by not translating their meaning.

In the second verse, the *Jalālayn* puts the clarifying word *hāda* (this) when the Qur'an says *dālika* (that), to remind the reader that what God means by *dālika* here is 'this book' that you are reading. Then, when the Qur'an says *al-kitāb* (the book), *Jalālayn* clarifies that 'the book is the one read by Muhammad', not the other *kitab* (Bible or Torah, for example). After that, we find how *Jalālayn* 'helps' non-Arab translators of the Qur'an with synonyms for difficult words. The Quranic word *rayb* (doubt, suspicion, uncertainty) (Wehr and Cowan 1976: 370) is 'translated' by *Jalālayn* as *šak* (doubt, suspicion, uncertainty, misgiving) (ibid.: 481). These practices are, in fact, an intralingual translation.

In addition to providing an authoritative explanation of the meaning of the Qur'an, *Jalālayn* operates on grammatical and linguistic layers like typical translation works. *Jalālayn* can be the basis for finding where the Qur'an is translatable, while it also defines where it is 'untranslatable'. These two functions set 'precedence' for others to start a project in other languages. While translating the Qur'an into other languages is considered illegitimate, the *tafsīr* is not. As I pointed out, translation to other languages becomes possible through the door of *tafsīr*.

Jalālayn learning as a translation practice

The primary process of studying the *Jalālayn* in a *pesantren* or *surau* is translating both the Qur'an and *Jalālayn* texts into Javanese or Malay. The manuscripts of the *Jalālayn* show that the primary method used is an interlinear translation, known as *makna gandhul* in Javanese which uses a text's grammatical and non-grammatical elements to achieve precise and authoritative meaning. With the help of the *Jalālayn*, Indonesian readers can find the Quranic meaning from a richer resource.

On its surface, the interlinear translation of *terjemahan gandhul* seems like a typical word-for-word translation, but if we consider the oral aspect of the translation practice, *terjemah gandhul* is more than this. A word has never been translated in isolation. In the tradition of *terjemah gandhul*, there are at least three strategies employed to keep a word connected to other words or a context: (1) in the oral reading technique, (2) in defining its grammatical positions, and (3) in putting the reference markers.

In the oral practice of the *bandongan* model, the *kiai* would read the *Jalālayn* text in a particular way of reading, by which he gives the translation after a specific grammatical unit. For example, when he reads the sentence *al-ḥamdu lillāh* he reads it into two units of reading and translation.

- *Al-ḥamdu – utawi sekabehing puji*. He would pick the sentence's subject (*al-ḥamdu*) and give its meaning. He starts the translation by stating the grammatical position '*utawi*' to identify the sentence's subject. *Utawi*, in *makna gandhul* method, is a word used to mark the subject of a sentence.
- *Iku – lillāh – kagungane Allah*. Before translating the phrase *lillāh*, he starts with *iku* to mark the word as the predicate (*khabar*) of the sentence. After that grammatical statement, he translates the predicative phrase *lillāh* (*kagungane Allah*).

In this example of oral reading, the *kiai* must analyse the grammatical unit so that he knows where to read the Arabic text and where to translate it according to its grammatical units. The manuscripts provided ample evidence of this practice of identifying the grammatical status of words in a sentence. In addition to particular terms, such as *utawi* and *iku* in the previous example, the *Jalālayn* manuscripts also provide other grammatical marks. My findings from a random survey of various manuscripts are in Table 3. Most of these results are from Javanese manuscripts, as I cannot find similar markers in the Sumatran manuscripts.

Table 3. Grammatical codes from the manuscripts.

No.	Grammatical marks	Reading	Grammatical position
1	اتوى	<i>utawi</i>	<i>mubtadā'</i> (subject of nominal sentence)
2	سف	<i>sapa</i>	<i>fā'il</i> (human subject of verbal sentence)
3	أف	<i>apa</i>	<i>fā'il</i> (non-human subject of verbal sentence)
4	ايكو	<i>iku</i>	<i>khabar</i> (predicate)
5	اع	<i>ing</i>	<i>maf'ul</i> (object)
6	حلى or حالى	<i>hale</i>	<i>ḥāl</i> (circumstantial adverb)
7	بيانى	<i>bayane</i>	<i>bayān</i> (explanation)
8	اكن	<i>akan</i>	<i>maf'ul</i> (object)

The practice of interlinear translation allows students to understand the Qur'an more comprehensively than reading a dedicated translation like *Tarjumān*. Presenting the Qur'anic text accompanied by an interlingual translation of the *Jalālayn* enables readers to directly experience the word of God and its 'authentic' meaning, which they learn through an integrated, inseparable translation process within a single manuscript. The interlinear method, as Basalamah suggested, can anticipate translation errors. In summary, this practice of interlinear translation of the *Jalālayn* may be more successful in dealing with the untranslatability of the Qur'an. According to Ronit Ricci (2016: 69):

Interlinear translation does not contradict the idea that 'perfect' translation is utopian. It does, however, come closer to 'success' than other translation models in its attempts to overcome the problem of untranslatability, to find equivalents for even small grammatical particles like prepositions or suffixes, an attempt that can go so far in trying to replicate the original text's syntax that the translated sentence compromises its semantic meaning

In the case of Bible translation, Walter Benjamin in his 1926 essay 'The task of the translator', quoted in Emily Dalgarno (2006: 145) praises interlinear translation, 'to some degree all great texts contain their potential translation between the lines The interlinear version of the Scriptures is the prototype or ideal of all translation.' Benjamin's emphasis on interlinear translation for the Bible stems from his belief that the Scriptures are foundational text that has been translated and re-translated countless times over the centuries. He argues that the interlinear version of the Bible captures the essence of the original text in a way that other translations do not (ibid.).

In addition to the interlinear translation of Arabic to Malay or Javanese, *Jalālayn* learning also provides an inter-semiotic translation. Orally, the teacher must explain the verse more than the literal translation. Depending on his educational background and personal expertise, a *kiai* would explain the *Jalālayn* text accordingly. There is one story about Kiai Bisri Mustofa, the author of the Javanese commentary *al-Ibrīz*. When he was a young *santri* in Kediri, East Java, Kiai Bisri Mustofa learned the *Jalālayn* from Kiai Ma'ruf of Kedonglo. What young Bisri loved about this *kiai* from Kedunglo (Kediri, East Java) was that he would give *ijazah* (a religious 'license') on special prayers taken from the Qur'anic verses while he taught the *Jalālayn* (Kuliah al-Islam 2021). Other *kiai* with Arabic grammar expertise might explain more about the linguistic aspects of the *tafsir*.

The practice of inter-semiotic translation in the manuscripts can also be found on the marginal notes. At this point, the manuscripts from the *pesantren* and *surau* give ample evidence of using other *tafsir* to further translate the Qur'an interlingually by the *kiai* or teachers in educational settings where *Jalālayn* was studied. Like the famous *Tarjumān*, the manuscripts do not consistently credit the sources of their quotations, but some do. As these manuscripts were for personal use, some were credited only with single letters, such as ب or ض or just one word (such as *جمل*)

The coded *جمل* is one of the most cited works as it frequently appears in EAP 061-1-7, EAP061-1-105, EAP061-1-106, and EAP061-1-122.⁸ To check who *جمل* is, I take one instance from EAP061-1-7, folio 12, where *جمل* is quoted here as: '*qawluhu [wa hal al-murādu al-i'lām bi dalika] ay bi-tubut al-ḥamdu lillāh, ay al-ikhbār bihi, wa haza al-iḥtimāl ...*'. I found that this note is an exact quote from another *tafsir*, *al-futūḥāt al-ilāhiyyah* of Sulaymān al-'Ajlī al-Jamal (2018: 386). The *جمل* then is an abbreviation that refers to his well known name al-Jamal. In summary, these marginal notes and references enrich our understanding of how these manuscripts were used for personal study. They also provide valuable insights into the sources and explanations that students and scholars relied upon in their quest for a deeper understanding of the Qur'an and its teachings.

Conclusion

The manuscripts from the EAP projects and collections provide a glimpse into the learning practices in the *pesantren* in Java and *surau* in Sumatra in the late 19th century. Most of the manuscripts from the *pesantren* have pedagogical notes, indicating a strong emphasis on structured and supervised learning. The learning methods in the *pesantren* included *sorogan*, *bandongan*, and *musyawarah*, with *bandongan* being the primary system. But the *surau* were found to have less structured and less supervised learning methods and were quickly challenged by colonial political pressure and internal reform movements in education. These differences in learning practices can be attributed to the historical context and each educational system's challenges.

Based on the manuscripts, it can be argued that *Jalālayn*-learning was used to educate students to be devout Muslims and potential Islamic teachers and to translate the Qur'an in a way

⁸ I suggest further research to delve deeper into these materials. But in the meantime, we may draw a quick conclusion of the most cited sources in the manuscripts in the examples given in the text.

that addresses the need for translation despite its perceived untranslatability. This learning method provides non-Arabic-speaking Muslims with a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the Qur'an than a regular translation could. Unlike traditional translations such as *Al Qur'an dan terjemahnya*, the *Jalālayn*-learning integrates oral, literal, and practical methods for translation. The outcome is not a translated text but rather a student who can preserve Qur'anic knowledge and pass it down from generation to generation in countries where Arabic is not the native language.

Translating the Qur'an is a complex process beyond the simple transfer of meaning from one language to another. Roman Jakobson (2012) proposed three types of translations: intralingual, interlingual, and inter-semiotic. When it comes to the untranslatability of the Qur'an, the *Jalālayn* manuscripts and their learning can be considered a 'translation' in all three types of translations. Its original Arabic *tafsīr*, the *Jalālayn*, is an intralingual and inter-semiotic translation. It provides a word-by-word translation from Arabic to Arabic for difficult words. It also operates on the semiotic level by using various knowledge systems beyond the Quranic texts, such as previous authorities, other *tafsīr* or reasoning. The Javanese and Malay translations in *pesantren* and *surau* provide interlingual translations and operate on an inter-semiotic level.

This study raises further questions for exploration. For instance, the findings suggest the significance of non-*Jalālayn* commentaries as evidenced in the marginal notes. It would be valuable to determine their titles, reference frequency, and regional distribution to gauge the impact of these commentaries. Another area of inquiry would be the exploring of the effects of studying *Jalālayn* on Quranic interpretation and translation in Indonesia. Previous research has analysed the *Jalālayn*'s influence on *Tarjumān*, but it remains unclear whether it has similarly impacted other interpretations and translation works.

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Note on contributor

Arif Maftuhin is a professor of Islamic law at the State Islamic University of Sunan Kalijaga, Yogyakarta. He has published numerous works covering various classical and contemporary Islamic studies. His dissertation, which delves into Islamic historiography, focuses on the *manāqib* literature of the *fuqahā*. As a postdoctoral researcher at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Maftuhin was involved in the 'Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies' project under the supervision of Prof. Ronit Ricci. Email: maftuhin@uin-suka.ac.id

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